

Long-Term Prognosis of Screen-detected Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm: A Cohort Study of Danish Men Aged 65-74

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Introduction

Background

Over the past three decades, three population-based, randomized controlled screening trials have been conducted in the regions of Central and Southern Denmark: the Viborg study ([Viborg] 1994–1998), the Viborg Vascular trial ([VIVA] 2008–2011), and the Danish Cardiovascular Screening trial I ([DANCAVAS I] 2014–2017) [1-3]. Baseline data show that AAA prevalence has remained stable across the three trial cohorts despite declining smoking prevalence and increasing use of cardioprotective drugs, particularly statins [4]. Similar changes in risk factors have been associated with declining AAA prevalence in other European countries [5,6].

Rationale

Follow-up for the full DANCAVAS I cohort is approaching 10 years, providing an opportunity to compare the long-term prognosis of screen-detected AAA across three cohorts from the same underlying population and screened in successive decades.

Objectives

- Compare long-term clinical outcomes in participants with screen-detected AAA across the Viborg, VIVA, and DANCAVAS I trial cohorts.
- Assess the associations of smoking status, statin use, and low-dose aspirin (ASA) use with these outcomes.

Methods

Study design

This cohort study combines data from three population-based, randomized controlled screening trials with follow-up from Danish national health registries. Analyses will include 8 years of follow-up, extending to 9 or 10 years where available.

Data sources

Viborg study

- Trial period: 1994–1998.
- Setting: Viborg County, Central Denmark Region.
- Study population: 12 639 men aged 65 to 73 years were identified through the Danish Civil Registration System. No exclusion criteria were applied. They were randomized 1:1 to receive an invitation to AAA screening or no invitation. Of the 6 330 invitees, 4 852 (76.7%) attended screening.
- Imaging protocol: Participants were screened at their nearest hospital with abdominal ultrasound performed by specially trained nurses using portable ultrasound scanners. The maximum anteroposterior (AP) inner-to-inner diameter of the infrarenal aorta was measured at peak systole.

- Management protocol: Participants with AAAs ≥ 50 mm were referred for computed tomography (CT) scanning and surgical evaluation. Those with AAAs < 50 mm were followed with annual ultrasound.
- Threshold for AAA repair: 50 mm.

VIVA trial

- Trial period: 2008–2011.
- Setting: Central Denmark Region.
- Study population: 50 156 men aged 65 to 74 years were identified through the Danish Civil Registration System. No exclusion criteria were applied. They were randomized 1:1 to receive an invitation to AAA screening or no invitation. Of the 25 074 invitees, 18 749 (74.8%) attended screening.
- Imaging protocol: Participants were screened at their nearest hospital with abdominal ultrasound performed by specially trained nurses using portable ultrasound scanners. The maximum AP inner-to-inner diameter of the infrarenal aorta was measured at peak systole.
- Management protocol: Participants with AAAs ≥ 50 mm were referred for CT scanning and surgical evaluation. Those with AAAs < 50 mm were followed with annual ultrasound.
- Threshold for AAA repair: 55 mm.*

DANCAVAS I trial

- Trial period: 2014–2017.
- Setting: 15 municipalities across the regions of Central and Southern Denmark.
- Study population: 46 611 men aged 65 to 74 years were identified through the Danish Civil Registration System. No exclusion criteria were applied. They were randomized 1:2 to receive an invitation to subclinical cardiovascular screening, including AAA, or no invitation. Of the 16 736 invitees, 10 471 (62.6%) attended screening.
- Imaging protocol: Participants were screened with non-contrast electrocardiography-gated CT at one of five regional hospitals. The maximum AP outer-to-outer diameter of the infrarenal aorta was measured at end-diastole.
- Management protocol: Participants with AAAs ≥ 55 mm were referred for surgical evaluation. Those with AAAs < 55 mm were followed with CT according to aortic diameter: every 6 months (50–54 mm), 12 months (45–49 mm), or 24 months (30–44 mm).
- Threshold for AAA repair: 55 mm.

*Some participants in VIVA may have undergone elective repair at diameters < 55 mm.

In addition to measuring aortic diameter, all three trials collected baseline data on risk factors, comorbidities, and medication use through clinical interviews and obtained blood pressure, height, and weight measurements.

Danish national health registries

Trial data will be supplemented with data from Danish national health registries. These registries can be linked at the individual level using each resident's unique personal identification number. Denmark's publicly funded health-care system provides universal access, and all hospital contacts are required to be reported to the registries, ensuring complete follow-up.

The following registries will be used: the Danish National Patient Register (hospital diagnoses and procedures coded using the International Classification of Diseases, 10th edition, and the Danish Medical Classification System); the Danish National Prescription Registry (which classifies drug substances using the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system); and the Danish Causes of Death Register. The registries used for each variable are listed in Table A1. Because the Danish National Prescription Registry was established in 1995, data on statin and ASA use may be incomplete for participants screened in Viborg in 1994.

Study population

This study includes men aged 65 to 74 years with screen-detected AAA measuring 30 to 54 mm from Viborg, VIVA, and DANCAVAS I. Participants with AAAs ≥ 55 mm are excluded, as they met the threshold for elective repair in all three trials.

Figure 1. Flowchart of study population construction.

AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm; Viborg = Viborg study; VIVA = Viborg Vascular trial; and DANCAVAS I = Danish Cardiovascular Screening trial I.

Variables

Primary outcome

- All-cause mortality: Death from any cause.

Secondary outcomes

- AAA growth: Rate of change in maximum infrarenal aortic diameter over time, calculated from serial ultrasound or CT measurements.
- Elective AAA repair: First elective surgical or endovascular repair of an intact AAA.
- AAA rupture: First hospital contact with a rupture diagnosis followed by either death or surgical repair within 7 days (to minimize misclassification of false-positive diagnoses).
- AAA-related mortality: (i) death from rupture recorded as the underlying or a contributing cause of death; or (ii) death occurring within 30 days after documented rupture or repair. Deaths are classified as AAA-related only if the most recent maximum infrarenal aortic diameter was ≥ 50 mm.
- Major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE)[†]: First occurrence of unstable angina, myocardial infarction, stroke, or cardiovascular death.
- Major adverse limb events (MALE): First occurrence of lower limb ischemia, lower limb revascularization, or major lower limb amputation.

Exposures of interest

- Smoking status: Categorical variable (never, former, or current).
- Statin use: (i) time-varying cumulative exposure, expressed in WHO Defined Daily Doses (DDD) [7], for time-to-event models; and (ii) mean daily dose (DDD/day) during follow-up for AAA growth models.
- ASA use: (i) time-varying cumulative exposure, expressed in DDD, for time-to-event models; and (ii) mean daily dose (DDD/day) during follow-up for AAA growth models.

In time-to-event models, statin and ASA use will be set to 0 DDD at baseline and updated at each redeemed prescription, accumulating throughout follow-up.

Selection of exposures of interest

Smoking status, statin use, and ASA use were selected as the exposures of interest because current guidelines recommend smoking cessation and statin and antiplatelet therapy for all patients with AAA to manage cardiovascular risk [8]. Although blood pressure control is also recommended, it was not included as an exposure of interest because associations between antihypertensive medications and AAA remain uncertain [9], and the frequent use of multiple medications in combination would complicate the analysis. In addition, blood pressure was measured only at baseline, limiting the ability to assess long-term blood

[†]Four-point MACE, with myocardial infarction defined to include PCI and CABG.

pressure control. Other variables, including diabetes and metformin use, were excluded due to the low prevalence of diabetes across all three cohorts. Body weight was measured only at baseline, making obesity or related measures, such as body mass index (BMI), less suitable as exposures of interest.

Covariates

All models will adjust for trial cohort (categorical: Viborg, VIVA, DANCAVAS I); age at screening (continuous, years); baseline maximum infrarenal aortic diameter (AAA size; continuous, mm); baseline pulse pressure (PP; continuous, mmHg); baseline body surface area (BSA; continuous, m²); diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease (IHD), peripheral arterial disease (PAD), prior stroke, and heart failure (HF), all dichotomous (yes/no).

Selection of covariates

Trial cohort is included to control for differences in trial protocols and calendar time. Age is a strong predictor of AAA risk, while baseline AAA size is strongly associated with risk of rupture [10]. PP and BSA were selected to represent blood pressure and body size, respectively. An AI-based model developed using Danish Vascular Registry data identified PP and BSA as stronger predictors of rupture than related measures, such as systolic blood pressure (SBP) and BMI [11]. Diabetes, IHD, PAD, stroke, and HF are included to account for pre-existing cardiovascular risk.

Baseline characteristics

Imaging modality (ultrasound or CT); baseline SBP (continuous, mmHg); baseline diastolic blood pressure (continuous, mmHg); baseline BMI (continuous, kg/m²); hypertension, chronic kidney disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (all dichotomous, yes/no); and use of antihypertensives, oral antidiabetics, metformin, non-aspirin antiplatelets, anticoagulants, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, and bronchodilators (all dichotomous, yes/no).

Table A1 lists coding definitions for outcomes, exposures of interest, covariates, and baseline characteristics. Assumed associations among outcomes, exposures of interest, and covariates are illustrated in Figures A1-7.

Sources of potential bias

Immortal time bias may occur if person-time before medication initiation is incorrectly classified as exposed. Statin and ASA use will be modeled as time-varying exposures in time-to-event analyses to minimize this bias. Some misclassification may persist because redeemed prescriptions do not ensure ingestion, although repeated refills would lessen this concern.

Healthy-user bias may occur if participants who adhere to smoking cessation, statin therapy, or antiplatelet therapy differ systematically from non-adherent participants in underlying health or lifestyle factors. This limitation cannot be fully addressed within the present design.

Confounding by indication is expected to be limited because many participants would have initiated statins and ASA after AAA detection at screening, rather than for pre-existing cardiovascular disease. Some residual confounding may persist.

Confounding by co-intervention is expected due to the frequent co-prescription of statins and ASA, making it difficult to isolate their independent associations. When analyzing one exposure, the other will be included as a covariate. Multicollinearity may limit interpretability, and a sensitivity analysis will be conducted to evaluate its impact.

Confounding by calendar time is expected because statin prescription protocols differed across trials, with higher doses being prescribed over time. To account for this, models will adjust for trial cohort, although some residual confounding is likely to persist. In addition, the lower repair threshold in Viborg compared with VIVA and DANCAVAS I may lead to overestimation of the elective repair rate in Viborg relative to the other cohorts. A sensitivity analysis will be conducted to evaluate the impact of the different repair thresholds.

Selection bias may occur if individuals who did not attend screening or follow-up imaging differ systematically from those who did. Its potential impact will be assessed by comparing rupture and repair rates between participants who attended follow-up and those who did not.

Statistical methods

Baseline characteristics

Baseline characteristics will be reported overall and by trial cohort. Categorical variables will be reported as frequencies (n) and percentages (%), and continuous variables as means \pm SD or medians (Q1-Q3), depending on distribution. Normality will be assessed using histograms and Q-Q plots. Differences between trial cohorts will be assessed using the Pearson χ^2 test for categorical variables (or Fisher's exact test when expected cell counts are <5) and the Kruskal-Wallis test for continuous variables. Baseline medication use will be defined as at least one redeemed prescription within 90 days of the index date. P-values will be presented for descriptive purposes only.

Long-term outcomes

For time-to-event outcomes, the number of events and incidence rates per 1,000 person-years will be reported by trial cohort and overall. Kaplan-Meier survival curves will be presented for all-cause mortality, AAA-related mortality, MACE, and MALE, provided that at

least five participants remain at risk throughout follow-up and that no individual participant can be visually identified.

AAA growth will be reported as mean annual growth rates (mm/year) and presented in boxplots by trial cohort. Extreme values that could risk identifying individual participants will be excluded.

Time-to-event analyses

All-cause mortality, elective repair, rupture, AAA-related mortality, MACE, and MALE will be analyzed as time-to-event outcomes, with the date of screening as the index date. For all outcomes, participants will be followed until the event of interest, or will be censored at death (when death is not the event), completion of 8 years of follow-up, or the administrative end date (dd-mm-YYYY).

Associations between the exposures of interest and outcomes will be assessed using Cox proportional hazards models. For each outcome, univariate models for the exposures of interest and corresponding multivariable models including all prespecified covariates (as described under *Covariates*) will be fitted. Associations will be reported as hazard ratios with 95% confidence intervals and presented in forest plots. The proportional hazards assumption will be evaluated using Schoenfeld residuals.

AAA growth analyses

AAA growth will be analyzed using linear regression, with each participant contributing one derived observation representing their individual growth rate. Growth rates will be estimated as the linear slope of aneurysm diameter over time using all available aortic diameter measurements. Both univariate models for the exposures of interest and a multivariable model including these exposures and all prespecified covariates (as described under *Covariates*) will be fitted. Results will be reported as adjusted differences in mean annual growth rates (mm/year) with 95% confidence intervals and presented in forest plots.

Model assumptions will be evaluated by inspecting the residual distribution for normality and skewness. If extreme outliers (absolute residuals ≥ 5 mm/year) are identified, a sensitivity analysis excluding these observations will be performed. If residuals show substantial deviation from normality, regression models with robust standard errors will be used.

Sensitivity analyses

To assess the robustness of the exposure-outcome associations, models will be refitted using all combinations of smoking status, statin use, and ASA use to evaluate whether their associations change when one or both of the other exposures are included. Associations for

each combination will be reported in a table (proposed format in Table A5) to assess consistency with the main results.

To evaluate multicollinearity, variance inflation factors (VIFs) will be calculated for all covariates included in the multivariable models using the rms package in R [12]. Covariates with $VIF \geq 10$ will be considered highly collinear, and models will be refitted excluding these covariates to assess whether results change materially. Covariates with $VIF < 10$ will be retained, and any remaining collinearity will be acknowledged as a limitation when interpreting coefficients.

To evaluate the impact of different repair thresholds across the trials (50 mm in Viborg and 55 mm in VIVA and DANCAVAS I), analyses of repair will be repeated in cohorts restricted to participants with AAAs measuring 30 to 49 mm at baseline.

All analyses will be conducted in R (version 4.5.2). A significance level of 5% will be applied, and no correction for multiple testing will be performed.

Ethics

The original trials received ethics approval from the Regional Committees on Health Research Ethics for Southern Denmark, and all participants provided informed consent. Under Danish law, secondary analyses of registry-linked data do not require new ethics approval or consent. Access to data will be approved by the Danish Health Data Authority. Pseudonymized data will be stored on secure servers within the Danish Health Data Authority, with access restricted to authorized researchers. All analyses, data handling and reporting will be conducted in accordance with Danish and European Union data protection regulations, including suppression of small cell counts to prevent indirect identification.

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<i>*Proposed formats for the final manuscript</i>	

Table A1. Variable Definitions and Data Sources

Variable	Source	Definition
Abdominal aortic aneurysm	Viborg, VIVA, and DANCAVAS I	An infrarenal anteroposterior diameter ≥ 30 mm measured using ultrasound or computed tomography
Outcomes		
All-cause mortality	The Danish Register of Causes of Death	Death from any cause
Elective abdominal aortic aneurysm repair	The Danish National Patient Register	SKS codes: KPDG10, KPDG20, KPDG21, KPDG22, KPDG23, KPDG24, KPDG99, KPDQ10, KPDQ20, KPDQ21
Abdominal aortic aneurysm rupture	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI713, DI718
Abdominal aortic aneurysm-related mortality	The Danish Register of Causes of Death	Death from rupture recorded as the underlying or a contributing cause of death OR death occurring within 30 days after documented rupture or repair (See ICD-10 and SKS codes above)
Major adverse cardiovascular event	The Danish National Patient Register and the Danish Register of Causes of Death	Unstable angina pectoris OR myocardial infarction OR percutaneous coronary intervention OR coronary artery bypass graft OR cardiovascular death (See ICD-10 and SKS codes below)
Major adverse limb event	The Danish National Patient Register	Lower limb ischemia OR lower limb revascularization OR major lower limb amputation (See ICD-10 and SKS codes below)
Baseline measurements		
Pulse pressure	Viborg, VIVA, and DANCAVAS I	Calculated as systolic blood pressure minus diastolic blood pressure
Body surface area	Viborg, VIVA, and DANCAVAS I	Calculated using the Du Bois and Du Bois formula
Comorbidities		
Hypertension	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI109, DI11*, DI12*, DI13* or ATC-codes [‡] : CO3A*, C08*, C09*
Diabetes mellitus	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DE10*, DE11* or ATC-codes ¹ : A10*
Ischemic heart disease	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI120*, DI121*, DI122*, DI123*, DI124*, DI125*
Unstable angina pectoris	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI200
Myocardial infarction	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI21*, DI249

[‡]At least one prescription redeemed within ± 90 days of the index date.

Stroke	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI61*, DI62*, DI63*, DI649
Peripheral arterial disease	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI702*, DI739
Lower limb ischemia	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI743, DI745
Heart failure	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI50*, DI110, DI130, DI132
Chronic kidney disease	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DI120, DI131, DI132, DN04*, DN06*, DN07*, DN08*, DN14*, DN16*, DN18*
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	The Danish National Patient Register	ICD-10 codes: DJ43*, DJ44*
Medications		
Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: C09A*, C09B*
Angiotensin receptor blockers	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: C09C*, C09D*
Beta blockers	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: C07*
Calcium channel blockers	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: C07FB*, C08*, C09BB*
Thiazides	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: C03A*, C03EA*
Oral antidiabetics	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: A10B*
Metformin	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: A10BA02, A10BD02, A10BD03, A10BD07, A10BD08, A10BD10, A10BD11, A10BD13, A10BD14, A10BD15, A10BD16, A10BD17, A10BD18, A10BD20, A10BD22, A10BD23, A10BD25, A10BD26, A10BD27, A10BD28
Statins	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: C10AA*
Low-dose aspirin	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: B01AC06
Non-aspirin platelets	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: B01AC* (excluding B01AC06)
Anticoagulants	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: B01AA*, B01AE*, B01AF*
Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: M0A1*
Bronchodilators	The Danish National Prescription Registry	ATC codes: R03A*, R03B*
Surgical procedures		
Percutaneous coronary intervention	The Danish National Patient Register	SKS codes: KFNG*
Coronary artery bypass graft	The Danish National Patient Register	SKS codes: KNFE*

Lower limb revascularization	The Danish National Patient Register	SKS codes: KPDH*, KPDP*, KPEE*, KPEF*, KPEH*, KPEP*, KPFE*, KPFH*, KPFP*, KPGH20, KPGH21, KPGH22, KPGH23, KPGH30, KPGH31, KPGH40
Major lower limb amputation	The Danish National Patient Register	SKS codes: KFNQ09, KFNQ19, KFNQ99, KNGQ09, KNGQ19, KNGQ99
Causes of death		
Cardiovascular death	The Danish Register of Causes of Death	Death from myocardial infarction OR heart failure OR stroke (See ICD-10 codes above)

Table of definitions, data sources, codes, measurements, and timeframes to be used in the study. ATC = Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical; ICD-10 = International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Edition; SKS = Danish Medical Classification System (Sundhedsvæsenets Klassifikationssystem); Viborg = Viborg study; VIVA = Viborg Vascular trial; and DANCAVAS I = Danish Cardiovascular Screening trial I.

Table A2. Baseline Characteristics of Participants with Screen-detected AAA in the Viborg, VIVA, and DANCAVAS I cohorts

Variables	Total	Viborg	VIVA	DANCAVAS I	P-value
Cohort					
Screening years					
Imaging modality					
Age (years), median (Q1-Q3)					
AAA prevalence, n (%)					
Baseline measurements					
Systolic BP (mmHg), mean±SD					
Diastolic BP (mmHg), mean±SD					
BSA (Du Bois, m ²), mean±SD					
BMI (kg/m ²), mean±SD					
Baseline AAA size (mm)					
30–44					
45–49					
50–54					
Mean±SD					
Smoking status, n (%)					
Never					
Former					
Current					
Comorbidities, n (%)					
Hypertension					
Diabetes mellitus					
Ischemic heart disease					
Peripheral arterial disease					
Prior stroke					
Heart failure					
Chronic kidney disease					
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease					
Medication use, n (%)					
Statins					
Low-dose aspirin					
Non-aspirin antiplatelet					
Anticoagulant					
ACE inhibitor					
AT2 antagonist					
Beta blocker					
Calcium channel blocker					
Thiazide					
Oral antidiabetic					
Metformin					
NSAID					
Bronchodilator					

P-values represent comparisons across the three trial cohorts. Viborg = Viborg study; VIVA = Viborg Vascular

trial; DANCAVAS I = Danish Cardiovascular Screening trial I; SD = standard deviation; Q = quartile; BP = blood pressure; BSA = body surface area, BMI = body mass index; AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm; ACE inhibitor = angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor; AT2 antagonist = angiotensin II-receptor antagonist; and NSAID = non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug.

Table A3. Cumulative Incidence and Unadjusted and Adjusted Hazard Ratios for Time-to-Event outcomes by Exposure of Interest

	N	5-year incidence (%)	8-year incidence (%)	9- or 10-year incidence (%)*	Unadjusted HR (95% CI)	Adjusted HR (95% CI)
All-cause mortality						
Smoking (never)						
Smoking (former)						
Smoking (current)						
Statin use (per 1000 DDD)						
ASA use (per 1000 DDD)						
Elective AAA repair						
Smoking (never)						
Smoking (former)						
Smoking (current)						
Statin use (per 1000 DDD)						
ASA use (per 1000 DDD)						
AAA rupture						
Smoking (never)						
Smoking (former)						
Smoking (current)						
Statin use (per 1000 DDD)						
ASA use (per 1000 DDD)						
AAA-related mortality						
Smoking (never)						
Smoking (former)						
Smoking (current)						
Statin use (per 1000 DDD)						
ASA use (per 1000 DDD)						
MACE						
Smoking (never)						
Smoking (former)						
Smoking (current)						
Statin use (per 1000 DDD)						
ASA use (per 1000 DDD)						
MALE						
Smoking (never)						
Smoking (former)						
Smoking (current)						
Statin use (per 1000 DDD)						
ASA use (per 1000 DDD)						

*9- or 10-year incidence will be reported where available.

HRs will be estimated using Cox regression models, with N indicating the number of participants included in each model. Adjusted models will include trial cohort, age at screening, baseline AAA size, baseline pulse pressure, baseline body surface area, diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, peripheral arterial disease, prior stroke, and heart failure. HR = hazard ratio; CI = confidence interval; AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm; ASA = low-dose aspirin; MACE = major adverse cardiovascular events; and MALE = major adverse limb events.

Table A4. Unadjusted and Adjusted Differences in Mean Annual AAA Growth Rates by Exposure of Interest

	N	Scans, n	Scans per participant, mean±SD	Unadjusted mean AAA growth (mm/year, 95% CI)	Adjusted mean AAA growth (mm/year, 95% CI)
Smoking status					
Never smoker					
Former smoker					
Current smoker					
Statin use					
Per 1 DDD					
ASA use					
Per 1 DDD					

Differences in mean annual AAA growth rates will be estimated using linear regression, with N indicating the number of participants included in each model. Adjusted models will include trial cohort, age at screening, baseline AAA size, baseline pulse pressure, baseline body surface area, diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, peripheral arterial disease, prior stroke, and heart failure. SD = standard deviation; CI = confidence interval; DDD = defined daily doses; and ASA = low-dose aspirin.

Table A5. Sensitivity Analyses of Combinations of Exposures of Interest in Time-to-Event and AAA Growth Models

All-cause mortality				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin + ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin ¹				
ASA ²				
Elective AAA repair				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin+ ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin				
ASA				
AAA rupture				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin+ ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin				
ASA				
AAA-related mortality				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin+ ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin				
ASA				
Major adverse cardiovasclar events (MACE)				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin + ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin				
ASA				
Major adverse limb events (MALE)				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin + ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin				
ASA				
AAA growth				
	Smoking	Smoking + Statin	Smoking + ASA	Smoking + Statin + ASA
Smoking (former)				
Smoking (current)				
Statin				
ASA				

¹Time-to-event outcomes: Cumulative exposure per 1000 DDD. AAA growth: Mean daily dose per 1 DDD.

²Time-to-event outcomes: Cumulative exposure per 1000 DDD. AAA growth: Mean daily dose per 1 DDD.

Estimates will represent adjusted hazard ratios with 95% confidence intervals for time-to-event outcomes and adjusted differences in mean annual growth rates (mm/year) with 95% confidence intervals for AAA growth. AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm; DDD = Defined daily doses; and ASA = low-dose aspirin. All models will adjust for trial cohort, age at screening, baseline AAA size, baseline pulse pressure, baseline body surface area, diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, peripheral arterial disease, prior stroke, and heart failure.

Figure A1. Directed acyclic graph: All-cause mortality.

Directed acyclic graph depicting[§] assumed associations among all-cause mortality (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis, AAA growth, and AAA rupture are shown as unobserved (white) nodes representing disease mechanisms. AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm.

[§]All directed acyclic graphs were created using DAGitty (Textor J et al. Int J Epidemiol. 2016;45(6):1887–1894. doi:10.1093/ije/dyw341).

Figure A2. Directed acyclic graph: Elective AAA repair.

Directed acyclic graph depicting assumed associations among elective AAA repair (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis and AAA growth, representing disease mechanisms, and surgical fitness, representing underlying health status, are shown as unobserved (white) nodes. AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm.

Figure A3. Directed acyclic graph: AAA rupture.

Directed acyclic graph depicting assumed associations among AAA rupture (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis and AAA growth are shown as unobserved (white) nodes representing underlying disease mechanisms. AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm.

Figure A4. Directed acyclic graph: AAA-related mortality.

Directed acyclic graph depicting assumed associations among AAA-related mortality (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis, AAA growth, and AAA rupture are shown as unobserved (white) nodes representing underlying disease mechanisms. AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm.

Figure A5. Directed acyclic graph: MACE.

Directed acyclic graph depicting assumed associations among MACE (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis is shown as an unobserved (white) node representing a disease mechanism. MACE = major adverse cardiovascular events.

Figure A6. Directed acyclic graph: MALE.

Directed acyclic graph depicting assumed associations among MALE (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis is shown as an unobserved (white) node representing a disease mechanism. MALE = major adverse limb events.

Figure A7. Directed acyclic graph: AAA growth.

Directed acyclic graph depicting assumed associations among AAA growth (blue node), exposures of interest (yellow nodes), and covariates (grey nodes). Atherosclerosis is shown as an unobserved (white) node representing a disease mechanism. AAA = abdominal aortic aneurysm.